

Product User Guide and quick start guide

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	2
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Purpose of this document.....	5
1.2 The EUSTACE project	6
1.2.1 Aim	6
1.2.2 Why EUSTACE?.....	6
1.2.3 How does EUSTACE achieve this?	7
2 Product Overview	11
2.1 Available temperature variables and related variables in the EUSTACE datasets	11
2.1.1 Temperature variables.....	11
2.1.2 Related variables.....	12
2.1.3 Local time or UTC?	14
2.2 Overview of datasets produced	14
2.3 Other EUSTACE products	21
2.4 Format of the EUSTACE data sets	21
3 Quick start guide	22
3.1 General information on EUSTACE datasets	22
3.2 How to obtain EUSTACE products.....	22
3.3 Format and how to read the data products	24
3.4 Working with Uncertainty Estimates	25
3.5 Things to be aware of when using the data (Assumptions and Do's and Don'ts)	25
3.6 How to acknowledge / reference the data	25
3.7 Where to go for help and further information	25
4 Sections for individual data products with further information.....	26
4.1 Satellite Skin Temperature Retrievals with added uncertainties	27
4.1.1 Global clear-sky land surface temperature from MODIS on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2002-2016.....	27
4.1.2 EUSTACE / CCI: Global clear-sky sea surface temperature from the (A)ATSR series at 0.25 degrees with estimates of uncertainty components, v1.2, 1991-2012	36
4.1.3 Global clear-sky ice surface temperature from the AVHRR series on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v1.0, 2000-2009.....	37

4.2	Global land station daily air temperature measurements with non-climatic discontinuities identified, for 1850-2015	38
4.2.1	Summary	38
4.2.2	Data sources.....	39
4.2.3	Quality assurance.....	39
4.2.4	GSOD and duplicates.....	39
4.2.5	Homogeneity assessment	40
4.2.6	Estimation of reporting resolution.....	43
4.2.7	Detailed format specifications	43
4.2.8	Guidance on the use of flags.....	48
4.2.9	Known limitations	48
4.2.10	Example of use of breakpoints.....	49
4.2.11	Where to go for further information	51
4.2.12	References	51
4.3	European land station daily air temperature measurements, homogenised.....	52
4.4	Gridded European surface air temperature based on homogenised meteorological station records since 1950	53
4.5	Globally gridded clear-sky daily air temperature estimates from satellites with uncertainty estimates for land, ocean and ice, 1995-2016.....	54
4.6	Global daily air temperature combining surface and satellite data, with uncertainty estimates, for 1850-2015	55
4.7	Coincident daily air temperature estimates and reference measurements, for validation, 1850-2015	56
5	Use case examples	57
5.1	Using EUSTACE temperature data for validation in climate model research.....	57
5.1.1	Introduction/background.....	57
5.1.2	How can the EUSTACE dataset be used in PRIMAVERA?	59
5.1.2	Results/examples from the PRIMAVERA project	60
5.2	Using EUSTACE temperature data for calculating temperature indices.....	60
5.2.1	Introduction/background.....	60
5.2.2	How can the EUSTACE dataset be used for LACA&D?	62
5.2.3	Results/examples from the LACA&D project	62
6	References	68

7	How to Cite the Datasets	70
Annex 1	Glossary of terms and acronyms.....	73
Annex 2	Step-by-step example of how to access, visualise and process EUSTACE data with the Climate4impact portal	76
Annex 3	Links to some useful websites and tools.....	77
Annex 4	Frequently Asked Questions	80

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

This **Product User Guide** (PUG) is meant as a practical guide for the data products of the EUSTACE project (see section 1.2) and to facilitate (potential) users in their exploitation of the datasets. It contains:

- descriptions of the datasets
- instructions on how to access and use the data,
- advice on what can and cannot (or should not) be done with the data,
- example use cases,
- links to useful tools, etc.
- examples of how to visualize the data, and process or extract data (coming soon)

For an overview of the methods used to produce the datasets, the interested user is referred to the scientific user guide (SUG) (under development).

This document is structured in such a way that you can easily navigate through it to the parts that are of interest for your specific use case, without having to scroll through the whole document. For this purpose in many places you will find links to go directly to the [table of contents](#) or to related content in other parts of the document or even to the scientific user guide (SUG). The links in the table of contents are clickable and bring you directly to the chapter or section of interest. At the bottom of each page you can find a link to take you back to the Table of contents.

A Quick Start Guide is provided in Chapter 3 of this Product User Guide. This is intended to act as a quick reference guide to where to find all the information required to get started with access and making use of the data. Experienced users of climate datasets in NetCDF format may only need this and the specific relevant product description in Chapter 4. However, we hope that this user guide also helps less experienced users and even those with no experience at all with the NetCDF-format to profit from the wealth of information in the EUSTACE datasets. To this end we have added example use cases (Chapter 5) and useful information on tools for extracting and visualising the data (Annex 2 and 3 coming soon).

1.2 The EUSTACE project

1.2.1 Aim

EUSTACE (EU Surface Temperature for All Corners of Earth) has produced publicly available daily estimates of surface air temperature since 1850 across the globe with consistent uncertainty estimates for the first time by combining surface and satellite data using novel statistical techniques. It also produced many other useful products along the way towards developing the global analysis and these are described here.

1.2.2 Why EUSTACE?

Day-to-day variations in surface air temperature affect society in many ways:

- Health and well-being: they can cause cold stress or heat stress.
- Food security: there is a link between surface air temperature and crop growth and animal health.
- Energy: they influence the demand for heating or cooling; high temperatures compromise the efficiency of solar panels.
- Commerce: they affect the sales of a large variety of products.
- Tourism: surface air temperature affects the attractiveness of a region, and the risk of bushfires.
- Infrastructure: extremes affect the functioning of bridges, railways.

However, daily surface air temperature measurements are not available everywhere. Satellite data can be used to estimate temperatures at locations where no ground (or in situ) observations are available. However, satellites measure surface skin temperatures and not surface air temperatures. To estimate air temperatures at locations where no air temperatures are measured, we need an understanding of the relationships between traditional (land and marine) surface air temperature measurements and satellite measurements, i.e. land surface temperature, ice surface temperature, sea surface temperature and lake surface water temperature. These relationships can be derived either empirically, or with the help of physical understanding.

Figure 1-1: Different surface temperature measurements used in EUSTACE. Skin temperature measurements from satellite are: land surface temperature (LST); sea surface temperature (SST); ice surface temperature (IST); and lake surface water temperature (LSWT). Near-surface air temperature measurements, measured in situ over land and ocean are: land surface air temperature (LSAT) and marine air temperature (MAT). From Merchant et al., 2013 community paper and roadmap: <http://www.geosci-instrum-method-data-syst.net/2/305/2013/gi-2-305-2013.html>

1.2.3 How does EUSTACE achieve this?

The EUSTACE project used new statistical techniques to provide information on higher spatial and temporal scales than have been available before, making optimum use of the information in data-rich eras. The final and intermediate products from EUSTACE below could be used in many applications (Figure 1-2):

- Global land station daily air temperature measurements with non-climatic discontinuities identified, for 1850-2015 (section 4.2)
- European land station daily air temperature measurements, homogenised (section 4.3)
- Gridded European surface air temperature based on homogenised land station records since 1950: dataset of daily air temperatures from 1950 onwards (E-OBS, by interpolation; Section 4.4)
- Satellite data with consistent uncertainties: Satellite skin temperatures with consistent uncertainty estimates (section 4.1)
- Air temperature estimated from satellite: Globally gridded clear-sky daily air temperature estimates from satellites with uncertainty estimates for land, ocean and ice, 1995-2016 (section 4.5)
- Information on the relationship between skin and air temperature over different domains and different seasons (see the Scientific User Guide)

- Gridded global daily air temperature combining surface and satellite data, with uncertainty estimates, for 1850-2015 (Section 4.6)
- Coincident daily air temperature estimates and reference measurements, for validation, 1850-2015 (Section 4.7; Matchup database)

Figure 1-2: Links between the different surface temperature measurements and EUSTACE products.

The various steps in the EUSTACE processing chain are described briefly below and shown in Figure 1-2:

1. Break-point detection: daily series of measurements of air temperature (made *in situ* over land at weather stations) have to be checked for discontinuities in time due to changes of instruments, re-locations of stations, etc. (non-climatic factors). Identification of these discontinuities or break points is needed to make spatially and temporally consistent estimates of air temperatures (see section 4.2). The data are also quality controlled and new information on the reliability of the break-point detection is included.
2. Homogenisation: With the help of the knowledge of break points, the air temperature time series can be homogenized. This means that the original time series are adjusted in such a way that the effect of the non-climatic factors is removed. This can result in an increase or decrease of observed trends in temperature. This homogenisation has been performed directly for the European station air temperature time series (see Section 4.3), which is new in a pan-European data set. For the rest of the globe this is included in the creation of the global grids in step 6.
3. Create E-OBS grids: the homogenised station air temperature time series for Europe are interpolated to create a gridded data set for Europe, the homogenised E-OBS dataset (see Section 4.4)
4. Estimate uncertainties of the satellite skin temperatures: satellite skin temperatures (see section 2.1.1) contain various types of uncertainties, which need to be propagated through the air temperature estimation in step 5. In this step the uncertainties are estimated for all surfaces in a consistent way, breaking down those uncertainties into components arising from errors with different structures (see section 4.1). This consistency across surfaces is new.
5. Relationship building: functions are determined with which the air temperature can be estimated from the satellite skin temperature over different surfaces and during the various periods of the year. This is done with the help of a selection of the station air temperature data and the satellite skin temperatures. Subsequently for all locations and days where satellite skin temperatures are available the air temperatures are estimated (see section 4.5)
6. Create global daily grids: in this last step statistical methods are developed to fill in the gaps for the days and locations where no satellite skin temperatures nor direct air temperature measurements were available (partly due to clouds in the case of the satellite data) and to estimate air temperatures more completely before the time period where satellite data are available (see section 4.6). This combination of satellite data and measurements made *in situ*, in a daily analysis over such a long period is new. For validation of this final dataset, an independent match-up data base is used (see section 4.7).

More information on EUSTACE products and methodologies can be found in this Product User guide in the indicated sections and in the Scientific User guide (under development).

2 Product Overview

In Section 1.2.3 a list of EUSTACE products was given. In this chapter a short overview is given of the data in these EUSTACE products. Section 2.1 describes the types of temperatures that are provided in the EUSTACE datasets, and also includes some definitions of other variables; some terms are used in different ways in different projects or situations, and so to avoid confusion we explain which definitions we use here (see also Glossary of terms and acronyms). In Section 2.2 the datasets are described with references to the methods used for producing them. Along with these datasets, EUSTACE also produced other non-data products, such as the relationships between air and skin temperatures. These are described in Section 2.3.

2.1 Available temperature variables and related variables in the EUSTACE datasets

2.1.1 Temperature variables

Satellites measure skin temperatures. This is the temperature of the surface of the earth which can be estimated (or “retrieved”) from the radiation given off by Earth and seen from space. This can be the temperature of the top of the canopy of a forest or the soil surface in an area with bare soils. At meteorological measuring stations, air temperature at a height of about 2 meters (also called surface air temperature), is measured by thermometers. The ultimate aim of EUSTACE is to construct a global data set of daily surface air temperature, using satellite skin temperatures and surface air temperatures from measuring stations.

Figure 2-1: Schematic presentation of the difference between air temperature and skin temperature.

In EUSTACE some datasets mentioned below (under "Satellite skin temperature retrievals") contain surface skin temperatures. Abbreviations used for skin temperatures are (see Figure 1-1):

- LST = Land Surface (skin) Temperature
- IST = Ice Surface (skin) Temperature

- LSWT = Lake Surface (skin) Water Temperature
- SST_{skin} and SST_{depth} = Sea Surface (skin) Temperature¹ and Sea Surface Temperature at a depth of about 20 cm

Skin temperatures always represent an area average to some extent and are not point data, unlike measurements made *in situ* at weather stations or by ships.

The other datasets mentioned in Section 2.2 contain daily surface air temperature information. These use the following definitions:

- minimum daily air temperature: lowest temperature measured during a day, often measured in the early morning just before sunrise
- maximum daily air temperature: highest temperature measured during a day, often measured in the early afternoon
- mean daily air temperature: this is defined in this project as the average of the minimum and maximum daily temperature (over land) for the estimates in the final dataset based on satellite and station data. In station data files often the average temperature based on hourly temperature data is presented. The average and mean temperatures may differ.

Minimum and maximum temperatures are only provided over land, and not for sea/ocean, large lakes and ice.

Abbreviations used for air temperatures are (see Figure 1-1):

- LSAT = Land Surface Air Temperature
- MAT = Marine Air Temperature

Air temperatures in EUSTACE products can be either point data (from weather stations) or area average data (estimated from satellite data or using statistical methods). The spatial resolution of the final global gridded air temperature dataset based on satellite data and station data is 0.25 degrees in latitude and longitude.

2.1.2 Related variables

2.1.2.1 Uncertainty

The terms ‘error’ and ‘uncertainty’ are often confused. Careful usage (following international standards; VIM, 2012) brings clarity to thinking about uncertainty information. Terms with precise definitions that need careful usage appear in *italic* in the next paragraph.

A *measured value* results from *measurement* of a target quantity, called the *measurand*. It is only an estimate of the measurand, because various effects introduce errors into the process of measurement.

¹ In practice, here we use satellite sea surface temperature estimated at a depth of 20cm below the surface, rather than the skin temperature. We do this to provide consistency with the long record of sea surface temperatures made *in situ*, which we use to understand the relationship between surface temperature and air temperature over the oceans.

These errors are unknown, although their distributional properties may be able to be characterized. *Uncertainty* information characterizes the distribution of values it is reasonable to attribute to the measurand, given the measured value and our characterization of effects causing error.

In short, the error is the ‘wrongness’ of the measured value. The uncertainty describes the ‘doubt’ we have about the measurand’s value, given the measured value and our understanding of effects causing errors.

Uncertainty arises from and propagates through every physical and data transformation involved in creating a dataset.

For the purpose of estimating consistent uncertainties in skin temperature retrievals across all surfaces of Earth in EUSTACE, uncertainty is modelled as three components²:

- “random” -- meaning errors that are both random and independent between all data
- “locally systematic” – meaning errors that are highly correlated across short separations in time and distance; statisticians may refer to this case as “structured random”
- “[large-scale] systematic” – meaning errors that have a structure that is persistent in time and space; this includes but is not limited to “biases”

Thus, the components are distinguished by their error correlation length scales. In truth, the division between locally systematic and systematic cases is somewhat artificial, and how best to decompose effects with a range of types of correlation into these components is a matter of judgement (see [Merchant et al 2015](#) for more detail). Information on the various uncertainty components is provided, but also a measure of total uncertainty.

These components of uncertainty are propagated separately through the gridding process and through the process of estimating air temperature from satellite skin temperature using the relationships understood to exist between skin and air temperature over the different surfaces. As well as taking into account uncertainties in the skin temperature used, this process propagates uncertainties in other information such as fractional vegetation cover (over land) and the mask used to exclude retrievals affected by the presence of clouds (over ice).

The above uncertainty components are propagated, where possible, through the process of creating global or European fields which have been completed using statistical methods of infilling. In this case, uncertainty is communicated by provision of an ensemble of gridded fields for each day which are all consistent with our understanding of uncertainties in the input data and the uncertainty in the infilling process itself. In this way, the correlation structure of the uncertainties is encoded, where possible, in the structure of the differences between the ensemble members and provides a convenient way for users to explore the impact of the uncertainties on their application of the EUSTACE data. Besides the ensemble, also a best-estimate of the daily air temperature and a measure of the total uncertainty is provided.

² For some datasets the local systematic uncertainty is subdivided into two

2.1.2.2 Observation Influence

The observation influence is a dimensionless quantity in the range 0-1 indicating the extent to which the daily temperatures in the analysis are influenced by observations. Where the value is close to 0, there are no nearby observations, or they are very uncertain, and the analysis is poorly constrained. The analysis temperature will revert to be close to the climatological average. Where it is close to 1, the value is well constrained by observations. The ensemble spread will be large when the observation influence is zero and small where the observation influence is one.

2.1.3 Local time or UTC?

A day can be defined in various ways, e.g. by local time/time zone, or 00:00-24:00 UTC. Countries regularly use different definitions for their observations (Van den Besselaar et al., 2012). The most appropriate definition may differ per type of user. In EUSTACE we use local time, since we assume this makes it easier for certain groups of potentially new users to use our data (based on feedback from users). Experienced users generally will know how to transform the local time into the Universal Time.

2.1.4 Daily time series and derived data

Some users, e.g. climate scientists, may want to use the data set with the daily data, but others may want to use derived data/information, such as climatologies, trends, etc. These derived products can be calculated with the help of the produced daily time series. Additional to this Product User Guide some examples are given on how to process the EUSTACE datasets³ into derived data using the Climate4Impact portal. This includes processing into derived data, but also e.g. selecting data for a certain region or period (Annex 2 Step-by-step guide for Climate4Impact).

2.2 Overview of datasets produced

The table below contains a summary of the final output products from the EUSTACE project which are described in some more detail just below the table and in more detail in Chapter 4 .

Short name	Descriptive Name	Dataset Link	Licence
Satellite⁴ skin temperatures			
Global satellite land surface	EUSTACE / GlobTemperature: Global clear-sky land surface temperature from MODIS	http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/0f1a958a130547febd40057f5ec1c837	Open

³ The examples do not include EUSTACE datasets, since they weren't available when the step-by-step guide was made.

⁴ Skin temperature estimates based on different satellites are available.

temperature, v2.1	Aqua on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2002-2016			
	EUSTACE / GlobTemperature: Global clear-sky land surface temperature from MODIS Terra on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2000-2016		http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/655866af94cd4fa6af67809657b275c3	Open
Global satellite ice surface temperature, v1.0	EUSTACE / AASTI: Global clear-sky ice surface temperature from the AVHRR series on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v1.0, 2000-2009	Coming soon		Open
Global satellite sea surface temperature, v1.2	EUSTACE / CCI: Global clear-sky sea surface temperature from the (A)ATSR series at 0.25 degrees with estimates of uncertainty components, v1.2, 1991-2012	Coming soon		Open
Surface air temperatures from stations or in-situ data				
European station measurements	EUSTACE/ECA&D: European land station daily air temperature measurements, homogenised	Coming soon		Non-commercial use only
Global Station Measurements	EUSTACE: Global land station daily air temperature measurements with non-climatic discontinuities identified, for 1850-2015		http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/7925ded722d743fa8259a93acc7073f2	Non-commercial use only
Validation match up database, v1.0	EUSTACE: coincident daily air temperature estimates and reference measurements, for validation, 1850-2015	Coming soon		
E-OBS	EUSTACE / E-OBS: Gridded European surface air temperature based on	Coming soon		Non-commercial

	homogenised land station records since 1950		ial use only
Surface air temperature estimates from satellites			
Air temperature estimates from satellite	EUSTACE: Globally gridded clear-sky daily air temperature estimates from satellites with uncertainty estimates for land, ocean and ice, 1995-2016	Coming soon	Open
Surface air temperature estimates from statistical analysis			
Global air temperature estimates, v1.0	EUSTACE: Global daily air temperature combining surface and satellite data, with uncertainty estimates, for 1850-2015	Coming soon	Open

Some further explanation of the above mentioned datasets is given in the following text:

Satellite skin temperatures:

- Satellite skin temperature retrievals: contains the skin temperatures for all surfaces of Earth as obtained in other projects (ESA DUE GlobTemperature, ESA Climate Change Initiative SST and FP7 NACLIM), but with new, consistent total uncertainty estimates (and estimates of uncertainty components split according to their correlation structure) across surfaces for cloud free days. Skin temperatures are obtained from different satellites (section 4.1)

Surface air temperatures from stations or in-situ data:

- European station measurements: This dataset contains homogenized and publicly available station data on air temperatures in Europe (minimum, average and maximum temperature). This is a dataset that is updated regularly with new and more recent measurements (Figure 2-4; section 4.3)
- Global station measurements: This dataset contains all publicly available station data on air temperatures with inhomogeneities identified where possible. It gives an indication in which year there are breaks and it provides a likelihood measure of the identified breaks (Figure 2-2; Figure 2-3; Section 4.2).
- Validation match up database: A surface air temperature match up data base for validation of the EUSTACE global gridded products (section 4.7).
- E-OBS: An in-filled analysis of European surface air temperature based on homogenised meteorological station records since 1950. The dataset interpolates the station data, taking into account differences in altitudes. This dataset is produced as part of the European Climate Assessment and Dataset project (ECA&D), and work undertaken during EUSTACE contributed to updates to this dataset. From version 20 on the data set will contain the homogenized

temperature data. The dataset also contains an ensemble to describe the uncertainties (section 4.4)

Surface air temperature estimates:

- Air temperature estimates from satellite: Surface air temperature estimates (with estimates of uncertainty) for all surfaces of Earth, derived from satellite surface skin temperature retrievals (for days and periods where satellite skin temperatures are available, i.e. clear sky days; section 4.5).
- Global air temperature estimates: These contain daily analyses of surface air temperature (with estimates of uncertainty) since 1850, based on combined information from satellite and in situ data sources. This dataset also contains air temperature estimates for days with clouds and for the period before satellite data were available (section 4.6).

Figure 2-2: Overview of regional spread of available stations in the EUSTACE global data set of surface air temperature measurements from meteorological stations. The size of the circles indicates the length of data available in a particular location. (Brugnara et. al, 2019)

KOEBENHAVN: LANDBOHOJSKOLEN

Figure 2-3: Example of breakpoint detection in the EUSTACE global station dataset for Copenhagen. A breakpoint is a point/year where the temperature changes for non-climatic reasons. This can be due to e.g. a change in location, change in instrument or a change in environment. (Brugnara et. al, 2019).

Figure 2-4: Change in trends in annual mean values of minimum temperatures after homogenization. Red circles indicate an increase in trend after homogenisation and blue circles indicate a decrease in trend after homogenisation. The size of the circles indicates the relative sizes of the changes in trend (Squintu et al, 2018).

Table 2.2 Some characteristics of the datasets in the EUSTACE-project

Short name	Further detail	Surface	Period	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Variables
Satellite⁵ skin temperatures						
Global satellite land surface temperature, v2.1	MODIS-Aqua	Land	2002-2016	on satellite swath	on satellite swath	Tskin
	MODIS-Terra	Land	2000-2016	on satellite swath	on satellite swath	Tskin
Global satellite ice surface temperature, v1.0	AVHRR	Ice	2000-2009	on satellite swath	on satellite swath	Tskin
Global satellite sea surface	ATSR-series	Ocean	1991-2012	0.25	daily	Tskin(depth)

⁵ Skin temperature estimates based on different satellites are available.

temperature, v1.2						
Surface air temperatures from stations or in-situ data						
European station measurements	Homogenized	land	1850-2019	stations	daily	Tn, Tx, Tg ⁶ .
Global Station Measurements	With break-point locations	land	1850-2015	stations	daily	Tmin, Tmax, Tmean
Gridded European station data	Based on homogenized station data, +100 member ensemble	land	1950-2018	0.25 & 0.1 degree	daily	Tn, Tx, Tg ⁶
Validation match up database, v1.0	Selection stations for validation	Land, ocean and ice	1850-2015	stations	daily	Tmin, Tmax
Surface air temperature estimates from satellites						
Air temperature estimates from satellite, v1.0		Land, ocean, ice	1995-2016	0.25	daily	Tmin, Tmax, Tmean
Surface air temperature estimates from statistical analysis						
Global air temperature estimates, v1.0	+30 member ensemble	Land, ocean, ice, lakes	1850-2015	0.25	daily	Tmean ⁷ ,

⁶ Tn, Tx, Tg are used in these products for the daily minimum, daily maximum and daily averaged temperatures respectively. The daily averaged temperature may be based on the average of the minimum and maximum temperature, but it can also be based on e.g, the average of the hourly temperatures. This has changed over time, and differs between countries.

⁷ The intention is to include later also the minimum and maximum daily temperature

2.3 Other EUSTACE products

In addition EUSTACE also produced the following products:

- Relationships between satellite surface skin temperature and surface air temperature observations for oceans, land, sea ice, ice sheets, and lakes. How these relationships are derived and which relationships are used is described in several articles;
- “Infilling” methods; The methods used are described in articles (in preparation);
- Coded and tested system for product generation;
- User guides for obtaining and using the dataset (this document and the Scientific User Guide). The Scientific User Guide contains information about the methods used to produce the various products. This document, the Product User Guide, gives more practical information about the datasets.

2.4 Format of the EUSTACE data sets

Please see the sections of this Product User Guide (Chapter 4) relevant to each EUSTACE product to find a description of their format.

3 Quick start guide

This section provides a quick reference section on obtaining and making use of the EUSTACE datasets. It is intended to be read both in conjunction with the Product User Guide (PUG), and as an independent reference guide for users starting to use the EUSTACE data; as such it contains pointers to the more detailed information available elsewhere in the EUSTACE product user guide.

3.1 General information on EUSTACE datasets

The final product of the EUSTACE project is:

- daily estimates of surface air temperatures across the globe from 1850 to 2015 with estimates of uncertainty.

Alongside this also other related products are made available:

- global daily satellite skin temperatures for land, ice and sea with components of uncertainty included;
- gridded daily air temperature estimates from satellite skin temperatures;
- global station air temperature data with non-climatic discontinuities identified;
- European land station daily air temperature with homogenised measurements;
- Gridded daily air temperatures based on the European homogenised station data from 1950 on (E-OBS);

Where possible, these data are made freely available to all users with no restriction. Due to limitations of use on some of the station datasets used as input in EUSTACE, the EUSTACE land station surface temperature products are only available for non-commercial use (see tables in Section 2.2 of the EUSTACE Product User Guide for licensing information and characteristics of individual datasets).

3.2 How to obtain EUSTACE products

The EUSTACE datasets are archived and made available from the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA), with the exception of the European Station data and E-OBS dataset (see below). Links to the location of the individual data products are given in Section 2.2 and in the relevant dataset sections of the EUSTACE Product use Guide. They can also be found through the EUSTACE project page in the CEDA catalogue at <http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/a52b2cc065a847b8a77a93896880349f>.

Open Access **Download** **See Related Documents**

Latest Info: 2019-02-22: The EUSTACE Product User Guide is currently under development. A version will be released here shortly, but in the interim, for further information on this dataset, please contact the CEDA helpdesk (support@ceda.ac.uk)

Abstract

This dataset consists of a global collection of land surface air temperature data from meteorological stations covering the period from 1850-2015. It has been compiled as part of the European Union Horizon 2020 EUSTACE (EU Surface Temperature for All Corners of Earth) project.

The dataset provides daily maximum and minimum temperatures from stations globally, brought together from a number of public databases: Global Historical Climatology Network Daily Temperatures (GHCN-D); European Climate Assessment & Dataset (ECA&D) non-blended; International Surface Temperature Initiative (ISTI); DECADE (Data on Climate and Extreme weather for the Central Andes); and ERA-CLIM (European Reanalysis of Global Climate Observations). These data have then been quality controlled through the removal of duplicates and unreliable data sources, and come with a large amount of additional information on quality, homogeneity and resolution.

Citable as: Brugnara, Y.; Brönnimann, S.; Good, E.; Squintu, A.; van der Schrier, G. (2019): EUSTACE: Global land station daily air temperature measurements with non-climatic discontinuities identified, for 1850-2015. Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, 22 February 2019. doi:10.5285/7925dad722d74743fa8259a923ac7072f2

Abbreviation: Not defined

Keywords: eustace, land surface temperature, station

Coverage

Temporal Range

Start time: 1850-01-01T00:00:00
End time: 2015-12-31T23:59:59

Geographic Extent

90.0000°
-180.0000° 180.0000°
-90.0000°

Related Records **Details / Docs (2)** Process Variables (0) Tools (3)

Figure 3-1: An example of a EUSTACE data product that can be obtained via the CEDA catalogue. Further information on the data product, licence and related documentation can be found under the ‘details’ tab. Data can be downloaded via the ‘Download’ link at the top of the page.

Data can be downloaded from CEDA via a number of methods as described below:

Web download from CEDA (<http://data.ceda.ac.uk>):

- From the individual dataset catalogue pages follow the ‘Get Data’ link at the top of the page.
- Individual files can be downloaded by clicking on the appropriate link, whilst multiple files can be downloaded using the ‘Download multiple files’ option towards the top of the page. To download large numbers of multiple files (amounting to more than 2-3GB in total), it is recommended to use the FTP download option instead (see FTP section below).
- A subset of the data in the files can be downloaded using the ‘subset’ link on the web page (see OPeNDAP section below)

Figure 3-2: Example of a screen where the various available datafiles for satellite skin temperatures from the EUSTACE project can be downloaded.

FTP:

- Access is available via the CEDA ftp site: <ftp.ceda.ac.uk>
- Note that a CEDA user account is required to access data via ftp. Users can sign up for this at www.ceda.ac.uk

OPeNDAP:

Coming soon

E-OBS and European station measurement data:

- E-OBS gridded data and European station data will also soon be available directly through ECA&D. Links to both these products are also contained in the relevant CEDA page.

Other data access methods: In the future, it may also be possible for some data products to be accessed and visualised directly through some external portals (e.g. the climate4impact portal). For a step-by step example see Annex 2 (coming soon).

3.3 Format and how to read the data products

The data is supplied in NetCDF format and follows the CF-convention. It can be read in by any standard NetCDF reading tools. The exact format for each product is described in more detail in the individual product sections later in this document.

Some suggested common tools to browse NetCDF data are: Coming soon

3.4 Working with Uncertainty Estimates

A key aim of EUSTACE is to provide consistent uncertainty estimates across all surfaces of the Earth. These uncertainties can be expressed differently per product type, and it is important to understand the types of uncertainties described with the data and how to use them correctly. A brief summary is given in Section 2.1.2.1 of the PUG, and for more information please see the relevant sections for the individual products.

3.5 Things to be aware of when using the data (Assumptions and Do's and Don'ts)

For a detailed description of each data product, we recommend that you read the individual product descriptions in Chapter 4). However, there are some general things to be aware of when using the data, which are briefly summarised in this section.

- The station data products made available in our downloadable products only include those stations which are publically available for non-commercial uses. In the processing of the downstream datasets, a larger number of stations have been included in the analysis; unfortunately, we are not able to redistribute some of these stations. Due to the original data restrictions, the EUSTACE station data products are only made available for non-commercial use.
- For some products, data points are given in local solar time; in these cases the definition of a EUSTACE 'day' is local mid-night to mid-night. (See section 2.1.3)
- If averaging data, care needs to be taken to do this properly taking into account the uncertainties and any correlations between data points. For satellite data, averaging needs to account for missing days. For examples of how to do this, please see: to be added
- We would not recommend using the skin and air temperature products to study the skin/air temperature difference, as their derivations are too interconnected. The relationship between how the two variables are determined are described further in the Scientific User Guide.

3.6 How to acknowledge / reference the data

If using this dataset please cite the data as detailed on the relevant CEDA catalogue record, and given in the table in Chapter 7 of the Product User Guide. Please also cite the EUSTACE overview paper from Rayner et al. (2019; coming soon).

To refer to articles/reports describing the methodology and datasets look in the scientific user guide and in the list of references (to be added).

3.7 Where to go for help and further information

For further help on using EUSTACE products please go to sections per product in Chapter 4 where this information is given.

For further details on the processing of the EUSTACE products please also see the EUSTACE Scientific User Guide (coming soon), and published EUSTACE papers.

4 Sections for individual data products with further information

The following sections provide more detailed information on the individual output products produced within EUSTACE.

4.1 Satellite Skin Temperature Retrievals with added uncertainties

The satellite skin temperature retrievals for all surfaces of the Earth have been derived in the context of other projects (e.g. GlobTemperature, CCI SST, FP7 NACLIM), but within EUSTACE, new consistent uncertainty estimates across all surfaces have been added. The following sections describe the details of each of these sub-products, with further scientific information also available in the Scientific User Guide.

4.1.1 Global clear-sky land surface temperature from MODIS on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2002-2016

4.1.1.1 Summary

Land Surface Temperature data from the MODIS satellite instruments on NASA's Terra (EOS-AM1) and Aqua (EOS-PM1) satellites have been produced by the University of Leicester under EUSTACE and the ESA DUE GlobTemperature project [<http://www.globtemperature.info/>] with support from the National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO) [<https://www.nceo.ac.uk/>].

The EUSTACE MODIS products provide retrieved Land Surface Temperature on the original satellite measurement grid (i.e. Level 2 products). The Aqua and Terra datasets are archived as two separate data products, with each providing global coverage for the time periods from 04/07/2002 -31/12/2016 and 05/03/2000 – 31/12/2016 respectively. Data is provided on the MODIS swath with a pixel resolution of 1km at nadir.

For further information on the derivation of this product see the EUSTACE Scientific User Guide (under development)

4.1.1.2 Heritage of the data product

The first version of the product (Version 2.0) was produced by the University of Leicester and distributed by the ESA DUE GlobTemperature project as the GlobTemperature GT_MYG_2P (Aqua) and GT_MOG_2P (Terra) products. The LST retrieval algorithm was developed under the ESA DUE GlobTemperature with support from the National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO), whilst the method for estimating the components of the LST uncertainty was developed under EUSTACE. In Version 2.0 the uncertainty estimates are separated into three components based on correlation scales: a random component, a component that is correlated on local length and time scales, and a large-scale correlated component. The EUSTACE dataset is Version 2.1 and further separates the locally correlated uncertainty into atmosphere and surface components.

In both versions the LST estimates are retrieved from MODIS Collection 6 radiances downloaded from the NASA Level-1 and Atmosphere Archive & Distribution System (LAADS) Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC) [<https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/>]. Further information on the processing is provided in the EUSTACE Scientific User Guide.

4.1.1.3 Access to Data

The data are archived at the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis and can be accessed and downloaded as described in Section 3.2 above.

Table 4-1: Links to the EUSTACE/GlobTemperature global clear-sky land surface skin temperature data from MODIS with estimates of uncertainty components.

Data Product	CEDA catalogue record	Download links
EUSTACE/GlobTemperature: Global clear-sky land surface temperature data from MODIS Aqua on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2002-2016	http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/0f1a958a130547febd40057f5ec1c837	http://data.ceda.ac.uk/neodc/eustace/data/satellite_skin_temperature/UOL/land/MODIS_Aqua/L2/GT_MYG_2P/v2.1/ ftp://ftp.ceda.ac.uk/neodc/eustace/data/satellite_skin_temperature/UOL/land/MODIS_Aqua/L2/GT_MYG_2P/v2.1/
EUSTACE/GlobTemperature: Global clear-sky land surface temperature data from MODIS Terra on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2000-2016	http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/655866af94cd4fa6af67809657b275c3	http://data.ceda.ac.uk/neodc/eustace/data/satellite_skin_temperature/UOL/land/MODIS_Terra/L2/GT_MOG_2P/v2.1/ ftp://ftp.ceda.ac.uk/neodc/eustace/data/satellite_skin_temperature/UOL/land/MODIS_Terra/L2/GT_MOG_2P/v2.1/

The data are in NetCDF format and follow the NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF)-convention (<http://cfconventions.org/>). The detailed format specification is given in Section 4.1.1.6

4.1.1.4 Working with the Data

This dataset comprises Land Surface Temperature data retrieved on the satellite orbit track. The data is at Level 2 (i.e. it is not gridded). There are two file types within the above directories:

- 1)LST...: This contains the primary data product of LST and its associated total uncertainty (example field is plotted in Figure 4-1), along with geolocation, viewing geometry and quality flag information.
- 2)AUX...: This contains the more detailed breakdown of the LST uncertainty estimates into four components (see below) as well as further auxiliary information that has been used in the LST retrieval, such as surface emissivity.

The data is split into 5 minute granule files consistent with those provided for the MODIS operational Level-1b and Level-2 data.

Using the Uncertainties

A pixel level uncertainty analysis is provided in each AUX file, which takes account of the expected performance of the retrieval algorithm under varying surface and atmospheric conditions. These uncertainties have been categorised into four components: random; locally correlated (atmosphere); locally correlated (surface); and systematic (Figure 4-2).

Table 4-2: Uncertainty components in the global surface skin temperature data files from EUSTACE

Uncertainty component	Definition	Contributions
Random (LST_unc_ran)	Uncorrelated in space and time.	Radiometric noise of the instrument and sub-pixel variations in the emissivity
Locally Correlated – surface (LST_unc_loc_sfc)	Correlated within same land cover type but appear random across different land cover types	Pixel-to-pixel uncertainty in emissivity across each landcover class
Locally Correlated – atmosphere (LST_unc_loc_atm)	Correlated on synoptic scales, but appear random on larger scales	Uncertainty in atmospheric state (primarily water vapour)
Systematic (LST_unc_sys)	Fully correlated across space and time	Uncertainty in the bias of the satellite surface temperatures relative to other data sources of temperature once all known residual biases have been corrected for

A total uncertainty, accounting for all components, is available in the LST file and is simply, for each pixel, the sum in quadrature of the uncertainty components assuming these are independent. Uncertainty components are provided so that the user can take account of error covariances when averaging the data to coarser resolutions (temporal and/or spatial). Thus, the total uncertainty on a spatial or temporal average (σ_{av}) over a sample of pixels of size N is given by:

$$\sigma_{av}^2 = \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{k=1}^K \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{ik}^2 + 2 \sum_{i=j+1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} R_{ijk} \sigma_{ik} \sigma_{jk} \right]$$

Here, N is the number of datapoints contributing to the average, σ_{ik} is the k^{th} uncertainty component on the i^{th} pixel and R_{ijk} is the coefficient of correlation of the k^{th} uncertainty component at the i^{th} and with k^{th} uncertainty component at the j^{th} pixel. Commonly, it is assumed that $R = 1$ for pixel separations less than some correlation scale and that $R = 0$ elsewhere. For the randomly correlated component the

correlation scale is zero and $R = 0$ for all pixel pairs. For the systematic component the correlation scale is assumed infinite and $R = 1$ for all pixel pairs. In the case of the locally correlated components the correlation scales must be estimated. It is likely that the errors in the LST due to errors in estimating the emissivity of a particular landcover type are correlated for pixels of the same landcover type although this may not be the case for similar landcover types on different continents (for example, deciduous woodland is likely to include different species of trees in different regions). Regarding LST errors due to errors in atmospheric characterization, these are likely to be correlated with atmospheric water vapour which has correlation scales of less than 10 km and less than 1 hour [Steinke et al., 2015; Vogelmann et al., 2015].

Figure 4-2: The surface locally correlated (left) and random (right) components of the LST uncertainty field shown in Figure 4-1

Quality Flags

The MODIS LST files contain a quality control variable (QC). This is a 4 byte integer with the bits corresponding to the following cases:

Table 4-3: Explanation of the Quality control variable in the MODIS LST files

Bit	Flag
0	Day / Night flag (day = 0, night = 1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Night is set where the solar zenith angle is ninety degrees or more
1	Consolidated cloud flag (0 = no cloud, 1 = cloud) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The best estimate is where primary (bit 6), secondary (bit 7) and thin cirrus (bit 9) are set to 0
2	Consolidated confidence flag (0 = good confidence, 1 = low confidence) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is set where either of the input split-window brightness temperatures have missing values or are suspect
3	Aerosol information available (1 = yes) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This bit is set to 1 since the information is acquired by the MODIS Cloud Product
4	Aerosol detected (1 = yes) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information acquired from MODIS Cloud Product
5	Spare bit for potential future evolution
6	Primary cloud mask – definitely cloudy (from MODIS Cloud Product)

7	Secondary cloud mask – probably cloudy (from MODIS Cloud Product)
8	Tertiary cloud mask – possibly cloudy (from MODIS Cloud Product)
9	Thin cirrus cloud mask (from MODIS Cloud Product)
10	Shadow flag (from MODIS Cloud Product)
11	Sun glint flag (from MODIS Cloud Product)
12	Non-optimum confidence flag where the pixel is produced but the quality may be suspect
13-31	Not used

To select only data of the best quality, it is recommended to use those values indicated as cloud free by the Consolidated Cloud Mask (QC Bit 1) and of good quality by the Consolidated Confidence Flag (QC bit 2). This accounts for both the best knowledge of cloud contamination and invalid MODIS radiance pixels.

Values where the total 'LST_uncertainty' field is greater than 2.0K should also be treated with more caution.

Known Limitations of the Data

When using the data, users should be aware of the following:

- Users should take account of the quality flag (as described above)
- The uncertainty in the LST due to failure of the cloud detection algorithm is not included in the uncertainty budget.

For more information on the data quality and validation methods refer to the ESA DUE GlobTemperature Validation Report [Martin and Goettsche et al 2017]

4.1.1.5 *File naming convention*

Product filenames follow the GlobTemperature file naming conventions (see GlobTemperature Product User Guide available from <http://www.globtemperature.info/>)

4.1.1.6 *Data format specification*

Detailed format specifications and metadata

The data are provided in NetCDF-4 format, and compliant with the CF-1.6 metadata convention. The data follow the GlobTemperature harmonised data format (see the GlobTemperature Product User Guide available from <http://www.globtemperature.info/>).

Two separate files are provided: the primary LST file and an auxiliary file.

1) The primary LST file holds those variables specified as essential by GlobTemperature, with the size kept to a minimum. Geolocation coordinates are specified to 4 decimal places (Table 4-4).

Table 4-4: GlobTemperature primary LST harmonised format (from GlobTemperature PUG)

Dimensions	Name
	time
	nj
	ni

Variables	Name	Type	Dimensions	Units	Comment
	jul_date	double	time	days	Reference time at start of datafile in Julian Days (days since 12h Jan1 , 4713BC)
	lat	float	nj,ni	degrees_north	Pixel centre latitude in decimal degrees north
	lon	float	nj,ni	degrees_east	Pixel degrees longitude in decimal degrees east
	dtime	int	nj,ni	seconds	Time difference from reference time in seconds with an accuracy of 0.1s
	LST	short	nj,ni	K	LST
	LST_uncertainty	short	nj,ni	K	total LST uncertainty
	QC	int	nj,ni	unitless	Quality control flags
	satze	short	nj,ni	degree	Satellite zenith viewing angle
	sataz	short	nj,ni	degree	Satellite azimuth viewing angle

2) The auxiliary (AUX) file includes extra variables, outside of the mandatory GlobTemperature variables (Table 4-5).

Table 4-5 Format of the auxiliary AUX files

Dimensions	Name
	Channel
	Nj
	Ni
	Systematic

ch_length					
Variables	Name	Type	Dimensions	Units	Comments
	LST_unc_loc_at m	short	nj,ni	K	Uncertainty due to locally correlated atmospheric effects
	LST_unc_loc_sf c	short	nj,ni	K	Uncertainty due to locally correlated surface effects
	LST_unc_ran	short	nj,ni	K	Uncertainty due to random effects
	LST_unc_sys	short	systematic	K	Uncertainty due to systematic effects
	channel	char	channel, ch_length	Unitless	channel description
	elevation	short	nj,ni	m	Elevation of land surface
	emis	short	channel,nj,ni	unitless	Channel emissivity
	lwm	short	nj,ni	1	Land water mask*
	solaz	short	nj,ni	degree	Solar azimuth angle
	solze	short	nj,ni	degree	Solar zenith angle
	tcwv	short	nj,ni	kg m-2	Total column water vapour

*Land water mask flag values and meanings:

(0) *Shallow Ocean* – ocean less than 5k from coast *or* more than 50m deep

(1) *Land* - not anything else

(2) *Ocean Coastlines and Lake Shorelines*

(3) *Shallow Inland Water* – inland water less than 5km from shore *or* more than 50m deep

(4) *Ephemeral* – intermittent water

(5) *Deep Inland Water* – inland water more than 5km from shoreline *and* more than 50m deep

(6) *Moderate or Continental Ocean* - ocean more than 5km from coast *and* more than 50m deep *and* less than 500m deep

(7) *Deep Ocean* – ocean more than 500m deep

4.1.1.7 *Where to go for further Information*

- EUSTACE Scientific User Guide (under development)
- GlobTemperature [<http://www.globtemperature.info/>]
- GlobTemperature Product User Guide available from <http://www.globtemperature.info/>

Points of contact for further questions: Darren Ghent (djg20@le.ac.uk) and Karen Veal (klv3@le.ac.uk)

4.1.1.8 References for 4.1.1

Ghent, D., I. Trigo, A. Pires, O. Sardou, J. Bruniquel, F. Göttsche, M. Martin, C. Prigent, and C. Jimenez (2018), ESA DUE GlobTemperature Product User Guide, Rep. GlobT-WP3-DEL-11, University of Leicester. [<http://www.globtemperature.info/index.php/public-documentation/deliverables-1/108-globtemperature-product-user-guide>]

Steinke, S., Eikenberg, S., Löhnert, U., Dick, G., Klocke, D., Di Girolamo, P., & Crewell, S. (2015). Assessment of small-scale integrated water vapour variability during HOPE. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 15(5), 2675–2692. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-2675-2015>

Vogelmann, H., Sussmann, R., Trickl, T., & Reichert, A. (2015). Spatiotemporal variability of water vapor investigated using lidar and FTIR vertical soundings above the Zugspitze. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 15(6), 3135–3148. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-3135-2015>

Martin, M., and Goettsche, F.M. (2017) GlobTemperature Satellite LST Validation Report (Report to ESA: GlobTemp_DEL-12_i3r0) [<http://www.globtemperature.info/index.php/public-documentation/deliverables-1/117-validation-report-del12>]

4.1.2 EUSTACE / CCI: Global clear-sky sea surface temperature from the (A)ATSR series at 0.25 degrees with estimates of uncertainty components, v1.2, 1991-2012

Coming soon

4.1.3 **Global clear-sky ice surface temperature from the AVHRR series on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v1.0, 2000-2009**

Coming soon

4.2 Global land station daily air temperature measurements with non-climatic discontinuities identified, for 1850-2015

4.2.1 Summary

The land station dataset is a global collection of daily maximum and minimum temperature series (Tmax and Tmin, respectively) covering the period 1850-2015. The series available to the user were obtained from public databases (hence, there is no data in this collection that cannot be found elsewhere).

The advantage over other similar collections is that the data have been “polished” by removing duplicates and unreliable data sources, and they come with a large amount of additional information on quality, homogeneity, and resolution.

The ideal user of this dataset is someone that is more concerned about the quality of the data than the quantity. Nevertheless, users have more than 30 thousand pairs of maximum and minimum temperature series to choose from (Figure 4-3).

Figure 4-3 a) Maps of the stations included in the EUSTACE land station dataset, where the size and color of the points depend on the length of the series. b) Temporal evolution of the total amount of data. Both public and non-public data are shown.

4.2.2 Data sources

This dataset is built on three pivotal public data collections:

- Global Historical Climatology Network (GHCN)-Daily (Menne et al., 2012)
- European Climate Assessment & Dataset (ECA&D) (Klein-Tank et al., 2002)
- International Surface Temperature Initiative (ISTI) (Rennie et al., 2014)

In addition, EUSTACE is among the first projects to include the DECADE dataset for the Central Plateau in South America (Hunziker et al., 2017), as well as the surface observations digitised during the ERA-CLIM project (Stickler et al., 2014).

4.2.3 Quality assurance

All data series underwent the 14 quality tests that are applied operatively to the GHCN-Daily dataset, as described in Durre et al. (2010). These include checks on basic integrity, outliers, as well as internal, temporal and spatial consistency. If a certain observation fails one of the tests, a quality flag is assigned to that observation (see table in section 4.2.7).

In addition to these 14 flags (one for each test), two more flags indicate data obtained from the Global Summary of the Day (GSOD) database and duplicates (see next section).

Geographical coordinates were verified semi-automatically by means of a Digital Elevation Model and a land mask; more than 100 sets of coordinates were corrected.

4.2.4 GSOD and duplicates

Global Summary of the Day constitutes an important source of GHCN-Daily. Daily data in GSOD are derived from synoptic/hourly observations, in some cases from only four synoptic observations per day. Hence, they are not actual daily extremes, but they have the advantage of being published in near real time and for countries that do not provide daily data. However, GSOD series are hampered by very large fractions of missing values, particularly in the early years (the oldest series dates back to 1929). Figure 4-4 provides an example of the difference between a GSOD minimum temperature series and a “real” daily series.

Figure 4-4: Difference between the minimum temperature series of Maquinchao in 1958 provided by the national weather service of Argentina and the minimum temperature series for the same station from the GSOD database. Data gaps are due to missing GSOD data. Note that GSOD data have a resolution of 1°F.

Duplicates are observations measured by the same instrument that are reported in two or more different series, sometime for different locations. This happens because the measurement and distribution of climate data is highly fragmented and disorganised, meaning that in most cases there is at least one intermediary between the station manager (i.e., national weather services and the like) and the global public collection. This also causes duplicate series to be slightly different from each other, depending on the time when they were acquired from the station manager and on the manipulation that they were subjected to before ending up in a certain global database. For the same reason, the measurement procedure (what instrumentation is used, time of observation, etc.) is usually unknown or very uncertain.

The EUSTACE station dataset does not include series that arise entirely from GSOD or are entirely duplicates of a longer series. When only part of a series is from GSOD or is a duplicate, then the entire series is retained and the respective quality flags are used for the affected part (see previous section).

4.2.5 Homogeneity assessment

A climate series is defined to be homogeneous when it contains only a signal related to climate variability. In reality, this is nearly impossible to achieve: the instruments, the observers, the procedures, the surroundings, and even the location of a station change over time. Hence, several artificial signals are usually part of a climate series. In most cases, these artificial signals are step-like functions caused by instantaneous changes in the station, so-called “breakpoints”.

Even if “perfect” homogeneity cannot be achieved, small inhomogeneities are tolerable for most applications. Large inhomogeneities, on the other hand, can significantly affect results, in particular for trend analysis. The homogeneity assessment is the procedure used to estimate the degree of inhomogeneity of a climate series.

Breakpoints can be detected statistically by looking for sudden changes in some statistical property of the target series (usually the mean). This can be done in two ways: by analysing the target series directly (absolute test), or by analysing its deviations from a homogeneous reference series (relative test). The former strategy is risky, because climate itself can cause step-like changes that could be interpreted as

breakpoints; the latter requires a suitable reference series (e.g., from a nearby station), which is not always available.

Since the degree of homogeneity of a reference series is in general also not known, the best way to perform a relative test is to repeat it several times using different reference series. Assuming that breakpoints occur randomly in every series, the agreement in the results will determine which breakpoints come from the target series (high agreement) and which from one of the reference series (low agreement).

EUSTACE brought this procedure a step further by looking at the agreement between different types of statistical tests, different variables, and different seasons.

Three different relative tests are applied to up to 8 reference series. A breakpoint is considered significant if at least 3 reference series agree on it. If not enough suitable reference series can be found, then an additional absolute test is applied.

Annual and semi-annual (October to March and April to September) means of T_{min} , T_{max} , T_{mean} , and the Daily Temperature Range (DTR) are analysed. Therefore, in the best case scenario 36 sets of breakpoints are provided for a certain series (3 tests X 3 temporal aggregations X 4 variables), or 12 sets when only the absolute test is applied.

Two additional sets (one for T_{min} and one for T_{max}) are obtained from “hints” for breakpoints in the data, namely changes in the reporting resolution, changes of source, and large gaps.

The user can combine the sets in any way that best suits his/her needs. However, a “recommended” merged set is also provided. The merged set combines all available sets to give the most likely position of the breakpoints (based on local maxima of detections). A measure of the relevance of the breakpoints, called “likelihood” index, is calculated from the number of detections from all sets within one year of a breakpoint. Figure 4-5 illustrates the merging with an example.

The likelihood index not only depends on the size of a breakpoint, but also on the ability of the method to detect it, given the information that is available (in particular, the reference series). An additional index, the “detectability” index, gives a measure for each year of the quantity and quality of reference series used. The detectability index is defined as the sum of the correlation coefficients between the reference series and the candidate series, hence its maximum value is 8. The results of the absolute test are used when the detectability index is lower than 4.

The breakpoints are given with annual resolution and their dates are all set on the 1st of January. As a consequence, an obvious limitation is that two breakpoints occurring in the same year or in consecutive years cannot be distinguished from each other. A finer detection of the breakpoints, for example by using visual methods, is recommended when attempting to apply corrections for the inhomogeneities.

BRENNER

Figure 4-5: Overview of the information provided for the station of Brenner, Austria. From top to bottom: raw daily Tmax series, raw daily Tmin series, reporting resolution, annual detectability index, number of detections. Crossed values in the raw data series indicate observations flagged by the quality control. Vertical dashed lines indicate the position of the merged breakpoints and the numbers on top of the bars indicate their respective likelihood index.

4.2.6 Estimation of reporting resolution

Temperature data are usually provided with a resolution of 0.1 Kelvin. However, in most cases the resolution of the thermometer that measured the data was coarser. The actual reporting resolution is relevant in some applications, in particular when calculating indices based on percentiles, and random white noise should be added to the part of a series that has too coarse resolution.

The EUSTACE dataset provides a rough estimation of the reporting resolution for each year of each series. In complicated cases the reporting resolution can change on a daily basis (due, e.g., to different observers working at the same station): what is provided in the dataset is the estimation of the coarser resolution that was used during the target year. For instance, if the data have a resolution of 1 K in January and of 0.5 K in the rest of the year, the estimated resolution will be 1 K. Insufficient data in a certain year results in a missing value for the resolution.

Typically, the resolution is coarser at the beginning of a long series and improves over time (see example in Figure 4-5), especially where electronic thermometers have been introduced.

4.2.7 Detailed format specifications

The dataset is organised in 166 temperature files (one per year) containing the observations and the quality flags, plus one “status” file for all years containing additional information on the series (such as the breakpoints).

TEMPERATURE FILES

DIMENSIONS

time	days since 01-01-1850
station	station progressive number (starting from 1, identical for every year)
name_strlen	length of station name (max 50 characters)
code_strlen	length of station code (max 50 characters)

VARIABLES

station_name (station, name_strlen)	Name of the station (not necessarily unique)
station_code (station, code_strlen)	Official station ID from source (unique)
latitude (station)	Latitude in degrees North
longitude (station)	Longitude in degrees East
elevation (station)	Elevation above mean sea level in m
data_source (station)	Source ID: 0. GHCN-DAILY VERSION 3.22 1. ISTI VERSION 1.00 2. ECA&D (NON-BLENDED, UPDATED OCTOBER 2016)

	<p>3. ERA-CLIM AND ERA-CLIM 2 PROJECTS</p> <p>4. DECADE PROJECT</p> <p>5. HOMOGENISED SERIES FROM BRUGNARA ET AL. (2016)</p> <p>6. DATA PROVIDED BY NATIONAL WEATHER SERVICE OF ARGENTINA (SMN)</p>
data_policy (station)	Is the data re-distributable? (0=Yes, 1=No)
tasmax (time, station)	Daily Tmax in Kelvin
tasmin (time, station)	Daily Tmin in Kelvin
tasmax_qc (time, station)	<p>QC flag, the following options are possible:</p> <p>0 (ok): Did not fail any quality assurance test</p> <p>1-14 (capital letters): QC flags as defined in GHCN-D (see Durre et al., 2010):</p> <p>D = failed duplicate check G = failed gap check I = failed internal consistency check K = failed streak/frequent-value check L = failed check on length of multiday period M = failed megaconsistency check N = failed naught check O = failed climatological outlier check R = failed lagged range check S = failed spatial consistency check T = failed temporal consistency check W = temperature too warm for snow X = failed bounds check Z = flagged as a result of an official Datzilla investigation</p> <p>15 (GSOD): Observation obtained from the Global Summary Of the Day (often unreliable)</p> <p>16 (duplicate): Observation already included in another (longer) series; used for partial duplicates</p>
tasmin_qc (time, station)	See tasmax_qc

<p>tasmax_definition (time, station)</p>	<p>Flag for how Tmax is defined, the following options are possible:</p> <p>0-14 (TX--): Definition codes from ECA&D: TX1: Maximum temperature unknown interval TX2: Maximum temperature 18-18 UT TX3: Maximum temperature 0-0 UT TX5: Maximum temperature morning previous day 06, 07, 08 until morning today (shifted 1 day back by ECA staff) TX6: Maximum temperature morning today 06, 07, 08 until morning next day TX7: Maximum temperature between 06 and 18 UT today TX8: Maximum temperature 21-21 CET TX9: Maximum temperature morning previous day 09 h GMT until morning today (shifted 1 day back by ECA staff) TX10: Maximum temperature from 2130 previous day until 2130 CET TX11: Maximum temperature morning today 9 UTC until morning next day TX12: Maximum temperature 19-19 UTC TX13: Maximum temperature within 00-24, 12-12 or 06-06 TX14: Maximum temperature 0-0 LT based on hourly intervals TX15: Maximum temperature 17-17 CET TX16: Maximum temperature 22-22 or 23-23 UT</p> <p>15-20 (ISTI_---): Definition codes from ISTI: ISTI_101: Daily value original ISTI_102: Daily value calculated from main standard synoptic observations (00, 06, 12, 18 UTC) ISTI_103: Daily value calculated from main and intermediate synoptic observations (00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21 UTC) ISTI_104: Daily value calculated from other sub-daily observations (at least 3 obs available) ISTI_105: Daily value calculated from other sub-daily observations (at least 20 obs available) ISTI_999: Missing/Unknown/Not Applicable</p> <p>-128 (missing value): No information available on definition</p>
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tasmin_definition station)	(time,	<p>Flag for how Tmin is defined, the following options are possible:</p> <p>0-14 (TN--): Definition codes from ECA&D: TN1: Minimum temperature unknown interval TN2: Minimum temperature 18-18 UT TN3: Minimum temperature 0-0 UT TN5: Minimum temperature morning previous day 06, 07, 08 until morning day TN6: Minimum temperature between 18 UT previous day and 06 UT today TN8: Minimum temperature 21-21 CET TN9: Minimum temperature morning previous day 09 h GMT until morning today TN10: Minimum temperature from 2130 previous day until 2130 CET TN11: Minimum temperature 19-19 UTC TN12: Minimum temperature within 00-24, 12-12 or 18-18 TN13: Minimum temperature 0-0 LT based on hourly intervals TN14: Minimum temperature 17-17 CET TN15: Minimum temperature 22-22 or 23-23 UT</p> <p>15-20 (ISTI_---): Definition codes from ISTI: ISTI_101: Daily value original ISTI_102: Daily value calculated from main standard synoptic observations (00, 06, 12, 18 UTC) ISTI_103: Daily value calculated from main and intermediate synoptic observations (00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21 UTC) ISTI_104: Daily value calculated from other sub-daily observations (at least 3 obs available) ISTI_105: Daily value calculated from other sub-daily observations (at least 20 obs available) ISTI_999: Missing/Unknown/Not Applicable</p> <p>-128 (missing value): No information available on definition</p>
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STATUS FILE

DIMENSIONS

detection_time	time dimension (annual resolution) for the detection score (days since 01-01-1850 of the first day of the year)
resolution_time	time dimension (annual resolution) for the reporting resolution (days since 01-01-1850 of the first day of the year)
station	station progressive number (starting from 1, identical to the temperature files)
name_strlen	length of station name (max 50 characters)
code_strlen	length of station code (max 50 characters)
tas_break	breakpoint progressive number for Tmean (starting from 1)
tasmax_break	breakpoint progressive number for Tmax (starting from 1)
tasmin_break	breakpoint progressive number for Tmin (starting from 1)
tasdtr_break	breakpoint progressive number for DTR (starting from 1)
merged_break	merged breakpoint progressive number (starting from 1)

VARIABLES

station_name (station, name_strlen)	Name of the station (not necessarily unique)
station_code (station, code_strlen)	Official station ID from source (unique)
latitude (station)	Latitude in degrees North
longitude (station)	Longitude in degrees East
elevation (station)	Elevation above mean sea level in m
data_source (station)	Source ID: as above
tasmax_reporting_resolution (resolution_time, station)	Worst resolution of Tmax observations within a year
tasmin_reporting_resolution (resolution_time, station)	Worst resolution of Tmin observations within a year
tas_break_time (tas_break)*	Year in which a breakpoint in Tmean was detected (days since 01-01-1850 of the first day of the year)
tas_break_station (tas_break)*	Station at which a breakpoint in Tmean was detected (station number)
tas_detectability (detection_time, station)*	Detectability index for Tmean
tas_break_type (tas_break)*	Type of breakpoint for Tmean (0=from the relative tests, 1=from the absolute test, 2=from metadata)
tas_break_season (tas_break)*	Temporal aggregation used to detect a breakpoint for Tmean (0=annual means, 1=Oct-Mar, 2=Apr-Sep)
tas_break_count (tas_break)*	Number of relative tests that detected a breakpoint for Tmean (1-3)
merged_break_time (merged_break)	Year of a merged breakpoint (days since 01-01-1850 of the first day of the year)
merged_break_station (merged_break)	Station at which a merged breakpoint was detected (station number)
merged_break_likelihood (merged_break)	Likelihood index for a merged breakpoint
detection_feasibility (station)	Feasibility of detection at a certain station (0=not possible, 1=only absolute test, 2=all tests)

* These variables are repeated for tasdtr (DTR), tasmax (Tmax) and tasmin (Tmin).

To extract breakpoints information for a certain series, the breakpoints IDs must be obtained from the desired *_break_station variable. Breakpoints affecting a certain series have adjacent ID (hence, the ID of the first breakpoint and the number of breakpoints are sufficient to extract the breakpoints information). What follows is an example of R code to extract the dates of the merged breakpoints shown in Figure 4-5

```
# load NetCDF library
library(ncdf4)

# target station code (see inventory file)
station <- "TX_SOUID103851"

# open NetCDF status file
nc <- nc_open("<path-to-the-status-file>")

# get station id
st_id <- which(ncvar_get(nc, "station_code") == station)
```

```

# get breakpoints ids
bp_id <- which(ncvar_get(nc, "merged_break_station") == id)

# get breakpoints dates using first id and number of breakpoints
breakpoints <- ncvar_get(nc, "merged_break_time", start = bp_id[1], count =
length(bp_id))

# convert to date format
breakpoints <- as.Date(breakpoints, origin="1850-01-01")

```

4.2.8 Guidance on the use of flags

Observations that have a quality flag different from zero should be discarded by most users. Some quality issues can be overlooked by the automatic quality control: when working on single series or a small subset, manual inspection of the series is recommended.

Some users might choose to ignore the flag 3 (I = failed internal consistency check), because this flag can arise from a non-standard definition of the maximum or minimum temperature (for instance, when the minimum temperature refers only to night time and the maximum to the daytime). In fact, the quality assurance algorithm assumes that both maximum and minimum temperature refer to the same 24-hour period. Hence, a series that was produced using a different definition is more likely to fail the internal consistency check. When this is the case, the flagged data might still be useful for some applications such as extreme analysis. However, it is worth remarking that the observations that have failed the internal consistency check did not undergo most of the other quality tests (see Durre et al., 2010, for details on the quality assurance algorithm).

The exact definition of the observations is provided for only a minority of series (from ECA&D) and is not always reliable, particularly for long series (for which the definition might have changed over time). When this information is relevant, it should be requested from the data owner, indicated in the documentation of the source collections. In some cases, however, tracing the data owner might not be possible: the best bet is then to contact the national weather service of the interested country.

GSOD data (quality flag 15) should be used carefully. It is not recommended to use these data when the entire dataset or a large subset is analysed. Duplicated data (quality flag 16) might be useful when analysing single series; however, the flags from the quality assurance are not provided for these data, therefore an additional quality control is necessary.

4.2.9 Known limitations

- Metadata, the information on where and how the data was measured, is very scarce due to the way climate data have been shared so far. Some of the data (most of those measured before the 1950s) were not measured following modern WMO standards, therefore the absolute values might not be directly comparable with those measured by modern weather stations. Besides, the precision of the geographical coordinates of the stations is often very poor and some erroneous coordinates have certainly been overlooked by the quality tests.

- The quality assurance is made using a fully automatic algorithm that is “tuned” to be rather conservative (i.e., to avoid false alarms). Hence, many erroneous values are not detected by the algorithm.
- The automatic detection of breakpoints is not perfect either, even when good reference series are available. For instance, breakpoints located at the edges of a series are less likely to be detected than those occurring in the middle. Moreover, as already mentioned, breakpoints occurring a few months from each other cannot be distinguished. For details on the performance of the breakpoint detection the reader is referred to the scientific user guide (under development).

4.2.10 Example of use of breakpoints

A typical use of daily temperature data is the analysis of trends in extreme indices. Here we show an example of how the reliability of these trends can be assessed using the likelihood index.

The upper panel of Figure 4-6 shows the trends of the number of hot days (days with Tmax above the 90th percentile or “tx90p” index as calculated with the R climdex.pcic package (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/climdex.pcic/index.html>) in all series in eastern Asia that are long (at least 48 years) and had sufficient reference series for the relative breakpoint detection. Generally the trends are positive (red colour), with some exceptions particularly in eastern China and south western Japan.

In the bottom panel we show only the trends for those series that do not contain merged breakpoints with a likelihood index greater or equal to 10 (note that this value does not have a particular meaning, higher or lower thresholds would give similar results), which we can consider “quasi-homogeneous”. Negative trends in China are mostly still there, while those in Japan have all disappeared. We can conclude that weak negative trends in hot days are locally observed in China, while in Japan they are the result of inhomogeneities in some stations.

The lower the likelihood threshold, the higher the probability that the series are homogeneous. However, a too low threshold will discard the large majority of the series, leaving not enough of them for a meaningful analysis of spatial patterns.

All series

Likelihood index < 10

Figure 4-6: Trends in the number of hot days over the period 1951-2010 for all series that underwent the breakpoint detection with relative tests (top panel) and for those that do not have inhomogeneities with a likelihood index larger or equal to 10 (bottom panel).

4.2.11 Where to go for further information

- Scientific User Guide (under development)
- GHCN-Daily website: <https://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/ghcn-daily-description>
- ISTI website: <http://www.surfacetemperatures.org/>
- ECA&D website: <https://www.ecad.eu/>
- DECADE page:
http://www.geography.unibe.ch/research/climatology_group/research_projects/decade/index_eng.html

4.2.12 References

Durre, I., Menne, M. J., Gleason, B. E., Houston, T. G., & Vose, R. S. (2010). Comprehensive automated quality assurance of daily surface observations. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 49, 1615-1633.

Hunziker, S., Gubler, S., Calle Fernandez, J. M., Moreno, I., Andrade, M.F., Velarde, F., Carrasco, G., Castellón, Y., Croci-Maspoli, M., Konzelmann, T., Rohrer, M., & Brönnimann, S. (2017). Identifying, attributing, and overcoming common data quality issues of manned station observations. *International Journal of Climatology*, 37, 4131-4143.

Klein-Tank, A. M. G., Wijngaard, J. B., Können, G. P., Böhm, R., Demarée, G., Gocheva, A., et al. (2002). Daily dataset of 20th-century surface air temperature and precipitation series for the European Climate Assessment. *International Journal of Climatology*, 22, 1441-1453.

Menne, M. J., Durre, I., Vose, R. S., Gleason, B. E., & Houston, T. G. (2012). An overview of the global historical climatology network-daily database. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 29, 897-910.

Rennie, J. J., Lawrimore, J. H., Gleason, B. E., Thorne, P. W., Morice, C. P., Menne, M. J., et al. (2014). The international surface temperature initiative global land surface databank: Monthly temperature data release description and methods. *Geoscience Data Journal*, 1, 75-102.

Stickler, A., Brönnimann, S., Valente, M. A., Bethke, J., Sterin, A., Jourdain, S., et al. (2014). ERA-CLIM: historical surface and upper-air data for future reanalyses. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 95, 1419-1430.

4.3 European land station daily air temperature measurements, homogenised

Coming soon

4.4 Gridded European surface air temperature based on homogenised meteorological station records since 1950

Coming soon

4.5 Globally gridded clear-sky daily air temperature estimates from satellites with uncertainty estimates for land, ocean and ice, 1995-2016

Coming soon

4.6 Global daily air temperature combining surface and satellite data, with uncertainty estimates, for 1850-2015

Coming soon

4.7 Coincident daily air temperature estimates and reference measurements, for validation, 1850-2015

Coming soon

5 Use case examples

This section provides some examples of applications that the EUSTACE products might be suitable for. The EUSTACE products have not yet been proven to be useful for these applications, but the following sections provide guidance on considerations that should be borne in mind when thinking of using the EUSTACE products for such applications.

5.1 Using EUSTACE temperature data for validation in climate model research

5.1.1 Introduction/background

Climate models are always run for a historical period and (often) also for the future to get an idea of the climate change that we can expect. The quality of the projections for the future can only be determined indirectly, since we, of course, have no observations for the future. For the past we do have observations, therefore the climate model runs for the past are compared with the historical observations. The final EUSTACE dataset (described in Section 4.6) can also be used for the historical temperature observations.

Figure 5-1 Schematic presentation of a climate model: the earth is subdivided in many grids in the horizontal and vertical directions: the climate model simulates the climate for each grid.

Climate models calculate the average of the climate variables over a grid (Figure 5-1). Grid size varies between climate models (Figure 5-2). In global models the spatial resolution is relatively coarse, although now also high resolution global simulations are under development with grid sizes of about 25 km (e.g. in the PRIMAVERA project⁸). Observational station data cannot be compared directly with the climate model data, since the station data give point measurements and the climate model gives area average data. This is especially a problem for precipitation data (since some rainfall is very local), but also for temperature in a spatially heterogeneous area this may cause difficulties.

⁸ For more info on the project look at the website: <https://www.primavera-h2020.eu/>.

Figure 5-2 Evolution of spatial resolution in Global Climate Models used for IPCC assessment reports (Source: www.wmo.int/pages/themes/climate/climate_models.php).

Figure 5-3 Differences in spatial resolution based on different data sources (E-OBS: based on interpolation of station data from ECA&D taking into account height) (Source: E. Good)

Station data are only available for a limited number of locations, whereas climate models simulate the climate for a large region or the whole globe. To overcome this, the following approaches can be followed:

- Station data can be interpolated in a sophisticated way (e.g. taking into account the effect of height on temperature, or the effect of the presence of the sea or large water bodies). The resulting gridded datasets give estimates of the e.g. area average temperature in the past at locations where no observations took place. An example of such a dataset is the E-OBS data set (see also section 4.4).

- Another way to create a dataset with a better spatial coverage is the use of re-analysis. In reanalysis the climate in the past is simulated with a weather model integrating as much observational data as possible.

- Use of satellite data. With satellites several climate variables can be measured, directly or indirectly. The advantage is the good spatial coverage and higher resolution (Figure 5-3). When measured indirectly the measured variable should be translated to the required climate variable. EUSTACE has developed such a data set, where the measured surface or “skin” temperature is translated to the air temperature.

In climate models every grid is assigned a certain “surface”: land, sea, ice, etc. To assign a grid to a certain surface a “mask” is used (Figure 5-4). Although the grid size has decreased considerably over time, it is still not exactly the same as in reality. In reality grids may contain two or more types of surfaces (e.g. land and ocean). The satellite observations used in EUSTACE are based on reality and in the project different methods are used to estimate the air temperature from the skin temperature above different surfaces. For a grid that contains in reality more than one surface, estimates of the air temperature for the various surfaces within that grid are made within EUSTACE. This is possible since the spatial resolution of the used satellite data is clearly higher than the final spatial resolution in the EUSTACE data set (about 0.25°).

5.1.2 How can the EUSTACE dataset be used in PRIMAVERA?

PRIMAVERA is working on high resolution global climate modelling. Several models will be run on a 0.25° spatial resolution and will be compared with coarser resolutions used until now. The idea

Figure 5-4 Left: hypothetical distribution of the “surfaces” ocean, land and ice over different grids.

Right: a way to create a “mask” where only one surface is assigned to a grid cell (in this case land (green) is used in preference to ice (light blue) and ocean (blue), and ice is used in preference to ocean).

behind this is that several processes may be simulated better due to the higher resolution. As part of the process of climate model development the model results are always validated. The currently available sources of data for the past-current climate do have some disadvantages:

- Interpolated station data: the E-OBS dataset is available from 1950 on, but it is available only for land and only for Europe. The dataset is available on a 0.25° or 0.10° spatial resolution and for determining the temperature per grid only the land surface is taken into account. Therefore, grids with sea and land only give the average temperature for the area over land. (An advantage is the availability of precipitation and sea level pressure)

- Re-analysis: currently available global re-analyses have a relatively coarse spatial resolution (<https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data/atmospheric-reanalysis-overview-comparison-tables>)
- Satellite based observational data sets: Until now these datasets were available for a limited period, the data were only available for a limited area and/or data were missing for days/periods with no measurements due to clouds. The EUSTACE project tries to overcome these shortcomings of satellite based data by creating a data set for all surfaces and using a sophisticated statistical method for filling in the days/period without data and for extrapolating to the past.

During the development of the data file structure for the EUSTACE products, someone from the PRIMAVERA project was interviewed. The final EUSTACE dataset (section 4.6) is interesting to them since it will be a global dataset covering all surfaces, and since it has a high resolution (similar to the one they use for their highest resolution runs):

- **Structure of the dataset:** Masks for land-water used in climate models are not the same as the real “masks”. This has to do with the modelling resolution (small island may not be explicitly included, Scandinavia may be connected with Denmark, etc.). Having estimates for air temperature for the different surfaces separately would allow them to make a dataset for validation with air temperatures for the same surfaces per grid cell as used in the climate model runs. This would allow them to make a better or “fairer” validation.
- **Use of uncertainty information:** For validation of climate model data it is important to have an idea of the uncertainty in “observations”: If there is wide variation in air surface “observations” (or estimates) then the simulated air temperature by the climate model may still be in the range of the “observations” although at first sight they may seem to differ a lot. This may clearly affect the conclusion about whether the climate model run has or does not have a (large) bias.

Validation of climate model projections is done by comparing the statistics produced by the climate model with the statistics of the “observations”, e.g. for the average temperature in a month, or for the highest temperature reached per year. In the final EUSTACE dataset information is given on the uncertainty per day, but also an ensemble is produced to describe the uncertainty. If one wants to take into account the uncertainty in the EUSTACE dataset for validation of climate model projections, the ensemble can be used best.

5.1.2 Results/examples from the PRIMAVERA project

To be added later

5.2 Using EUSTACE temperature data for calculating temperature indices

5.2.1 Introduction/background

On the basis of time series of air temperature (minimum, average and maximum; daily values) many different temperature indices can be derived. These indices are often used in specific sectors or used for a more general public. The indices give an (indirect) indication of the impacts of the climate or climate change. The (change) in e.g. the number of ice days (maximum temperature below 0 C) gives an indication of the accessibility of unpaved roads in Scandinavia during winter or the number of tropical nights

(minimum temperature of 20 C or higher) can be an indication of heat stress. At the website of ECA&D (European Climate Assessment Database; www.ecad.eu/) a large number of indices are generated (<http://www.ecad.eu/indicesextremes/indicesdictionary.php>). Similar databases are set up also for part of South America (LACA&D; <http://lacad.ciifen.org/>), and South East Asia (SACA&D; <http://sacad.database.bmkg.go.id/>).

Station data are only available for a limited number of locations, but people may also want to have data for their own particular location/village. To overcome this, station data can be interpolated in a sophisticated way (e.g. taking into account the effect of height on temperature, or the effect of the presence of the sea or large water bodies). The resulting gridded datasets give estimates of the e.g. area average temperature in the past in locations where no observations took place. An example of such a dataset is the E-OBS data set (section 4.4). However, the spatial resolution and accuracy depends very much on the density of stations (see Figure 5-5). For temperature, also satellite data can be used. The advantage is the good spatial coverage and higher resolution (Figure 5-3). Satellites measure “skin temperature”, although more often air temperature is used for indices. However, skin temperatures can be used to estimate air temperatures. EUSTACE has developed an example of such a data set, where the measured surface or “skin” temperature is translated to the air temperature by determining the relationships for several surfaces over land, oceans, ice and lakes.

Figure 5-5 Example from the ECA&D website for the maximum value of the maximum temperature in the year 2003 (high temperatures in a large part of Europe). On top: information based on station data; Bottom: information based on interpolated station data.

5.2.2 How can the EUSTACE dataset be used for LACA&D?

Where limited station data are available, the satellite data can be of added value for determining more local temperature indices, since they have complete spatial coverage (at least the infilled EUSTACE dataset, 4.6) at relatively high spatial resolution. For the land area where the Latin American version of ECA&D, LACA&D, is working, less station data are available than for Europe in ECA&D. The length of the time series may in general also be shorter. Besides, the EUSTACE dataset will also provide average daily air temperatures above other surface than land (e.g. the ocean). With the EUSTACE data various indices can be calculated at a higher spatial resolution than possible until now.

The uncertainty information that will be provided with the EUSTACE dataset makes it possible to calculate the uncertainty in the indices. For many indices the uncertainty cannot be calculated by just using the uncertainty measure that is given in the file with the “best estimate”. The value of the index depends very much on the absolute daily value: in the case of an estimated minimum temperature of $-0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a standard error (measure for the spread of the ensemble) of about $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ the values minus or plus 1 standard deviation would range from -0.5 to $1.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. When calculating the number of frost days (minimum temperature of $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or lower), on one side of the range the day would be considered a frost day, whereas on the other side of the range not. The use of an ensemble of time series, together describing well the total uncertainty would in that case be the most appropriate way to determine the uncertainty of the index “frost days”.

5.2.3 Results/examples from the LACA&D project

To be added later

5.3 Attribution of climate change

5.3.1 Introduction and background

Detection of climate change is demonstrating whether a climate has changed significantly, or in other words showing that the change is more than can be explained with natural variability alone. Attribution of climate change is the effort to scientifically determine what could be the cause of observed climate change. In most cases this focusses on determining whether the change could be due to the increase in Greenhouse gases (GHG) and not by natural variability alone. IPCC assessment reports have paid attention to attribution of global and regional temperature increases.

When extreme weather events occur, often the question arises whether the event is due to climate change. A single event cannot be attributed to climate change, but we might be able to indicate whether the return time of certain extreme events has changed significantly due to climate change or whether there is a significant trend in the likelihood of extreme events. One of the first studies on this so-called *event attribution* showed that the risk for a European heat wave such as in 2003 had clearly increased due to climate change (Stott et al., 2004). Methodologies for attribution of extreme events have been developed in several projects, among others in the EUropean CLimate and weather Events: Interpretation and Attribution (EUCLEIA⁹) and the World Weather Attribution (WWA¹⁰) projects (follow up of EUCLEIA). The projects try to provide information on attribution relatively fast after the extreme weather events have occurred, when there is a need and still interest from decision makers and the public. In both projects several types of extreme weather events are considered, including extreme heat and cold. Below we will indicate how the EUSTACE dataset can contribute potentially to the attribution of extreme warm and cold weather events. In between the description of the methods used for event attribution we describe in italics the potential use of the EUSTACE-dataset and the aspects that people have to take into account when using it.

5.3.2 Methods for extreme weather event attribution

To determine whether the probability of extremes has increased, long time series are needed and different types of climate data are combined (e.g. observations and climate models).

The first step in the attribution studies is to select appropriate climate indices. This can be a few-days-extreme (three-day maximum temperature average as used for the analysis of the European heat waves in 2017 and 2018; Figure 5-6) or multiple-weeks-extreme (as used in the analysis of record June

⁹ <https://eucleia.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.worldweatherattribution.org/>

temperatures in western Europe in 2017, or the two-week cold outbreak in northern North America). In some of these analyses, station data are used (for one location) and in others the average temperatures over regions are used.

If EUSTACE data are to be used for such analysis, this requires good representation of the extremes (maximum, minimum and average temperatures) at daily, weekly and monthly scales and good spatial representation (e.g. spatial extent of heat waves or cold spells). In the main EUSTACE dataset the best estimate is presented and also the “observation influence” is given. When little local information is available e.g. from nearby stations for a particular period, the observation influence will be high and the estimate of the daily temperature will be “smoothed” to the longer term average. The EUSTACE ensemble that is also produced will contain a better estimate of the extreme high or low temperatures¹¹.

Figure 5-6: The hottest 3-day average of the maximum temperature in 2018 (ECMWF analyses up to 24 July, forecasts up to 31 July) compared to the highest 3-day maximum temperature in the period 1981-2010 that is currently the “normal” period (based on ERA-interim re-analysis). Along coasts there are artefacts from comparing the high-resolution ECMWF analyses with the lower-resolution ERA-interim reanalysis (Source: <https://www.worldweatherattribution.org/attribution-of-the-2018-heat-in-northern-europe/>).

¹¹ In some areas the total uncertainty is under- or overestimated. In case of underestimation of the uncertainty the range of potential values in the ensemble will also be underestimated. Information about this is available in the user guide under validation.

The second step involves determining the probability of the extreme event in the recent climate (in the “normal” period: Figure 5-6 above) and its probability in the past when the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs) was much lower. Historical observations are regularly not available for a long enough period to enable such an evaluation¹² (NAS, 2016).

For determining the probabilities, observational data are used and a Generalized Extreme Value Distribution (GEV) or other statistical distributions are fitted and confidence intervals are determined (Figure 5-7 below). After this it is determined whether there are significant changes or trends in the occurrence of these extreme events (detection whether the climate has changed).

Figure 5-7: Example of the determination of the 3 day mean maximum temperature for station Madrid Cuatrovientos in the current climate (2017) and around 1950, for an event attribution study on the heat wave in southern Europe in 2017.

The EUSTACE dataset is a reconstruction of the weather in the past using observations, satellite data and the spatial differences between locations. The dataset represents an alternative to station data or re-analysis data for determining how extreme a certain event is in the current climate (often 1981-2010 is used). The EUSTACE dataset provides a clearly higher spatial resolution than the station data in most regions in the world. The newest re-analyses have a similar spatial resolution to the EUSTACE dataset, but they cannot always represent extremes very well. Especially in the period with satellite data, the EUSTACE dataset may have added value since spatial differences and extremes may be represented better.

¹² In model based approaches simulated weather and climate phenomena are compared under different input conditions: for instance, with and without human-caused changes in GHGs. Also combined approaches exist (NAS, 2016).

The EUSTACE dataset provides much longer time series and for many more locations in the world than with station data alone. As such the dataset may make it easier to determine how extreme a certain event is in the current climate and whether the probability has changed compared to periods with clearly lower GHG concentrations. However, in regions with relatively few observations in the past, the estimates of the daily temperatures will contain larger uncertainties and extremes are represented potentially less well. When determining the confidence intervals for the probabilities one has to take into account the uncertainties due to natural variability, but also the uncertainties in the estimates of the temperatures (with the help of the ensemble or the other uncertainty information). In such regions the combined uncertainty will be much larger and it will be more difficult to find significant differences in probabilities, especially for extremes such as the above mentioned 3-day average maximum temperature. This is also true for periods in the 19th century and in the early 20th century with relatively few station data.

During the generation of the EUSTACE data set inhomogeneities (or break points) in the underlying observational data sets are corrected for. Therefore, it is less probable¹³ that changes in probabilities in the EUSTACE datasets are caused by changes in station locations, changes in instruments, etc. (Figure 5-8 below for example of inhomogeneity).

Figure 5-8: Inhomogeneity in the 3-day mean maximum temperature for station Madrid Cuatrovientos in the early 1930's. With these inhomogeneities it is not possible to determine changes in probabilities.

¹³ As explained in section 4.2 not all break points can be detected, but the most obvious ones are detected, and are corrected for in the EUSTACE method.

Figure 5-9: Probability density functions showing different ways in which the climate can change, all resulting in changing probabilities of extremes (Source IPCC, 2012).

In the **third step** it is determined whether the change can be due to the increase of GHGs. When climate change is detected in step 2, it is not clear yet whether there is a relationship with the increase of GHGs. For the attribution, a link is sought with a factor that is clearly influenced by the increase of GHGs. The most obvious climate variable is temperature. For this in the statistical approach, global warming is factored in by allowing the fit to the distribution to be a function of the global mean surface temperature (GMST). Thus the probability density function is shifted up or down with GMST but does not change shape (Figure 5-9 above). In this way, it results in a distribution that varies continuously with GMST. This distribution can be evaluated for a GMST in the past (e.g., 1950 or 1900) and for the current GMST. If there is a clear relation between the climate index under study and the GMST (and thus with the increase of GHGs) the probability of the climate index under study will have changed over time.

In the methods used by EUCLEIA and WWA the observations are also compared with climate models that are available and suitable for the climate variables and regions under study. This allows to study better what is the cause of the observed change in climate. This requires that in the used models the variability of the studied extremes is compatible with the observed variability.

The EUSTACE dataset could be used to determine the Global mean surface air temperature and its change or the mean surface air temperature for a region.

The EUSTACE dataset can also be potentially used for determining whether the variability of the studied temperature extremes in the climate models is compatible with those in observations. This can only be done for periods and regions where we know that the day-to-day variability (and thus the extremes) is represented well (low observation influence in final EUSTACE dataset). This is probably the case for the period with satellite data and periods and regions with sufficient station data. Important for this comparison is also that the dataset is homogeneous. During the generation of the EUSTACE data set inhomogeneities (or break points) in the underlying observational data sets are corrected for as much as possible. Changes in probabilities in the EUSTACE datasets will, therefore, probably not be caused by changes in station locations, changes in instruments, etc.

5.3.3 References

- IPCC, 2012. Attribution of Extreme Weather Events in the Context of Climate Change. (Field, C.B., V. Barros, T.F. Stocker, D. Qin, D.J. Dokken, K.L. Ebi, M.D. Mastrandrea, K.J. Mach, G.-K. Plattner, S.K. Allen, M. Tignor, and P.M. Midgley (Eds.)). <https://doi.org/10.17226/21852>.
- NAS, 2016. Attribution of Extreme Weather Events in the Context of Climate Change. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/21852>.
- Stott, P.A., D.A. Stone & M.R. Allen, 2004. Human Contribution to the European Heatwave of 003. *Nature* 432(7017):610-4. DOI: · 10.1038/nature03089
- Otto, F. E. L., G. J. van Oldenborgh, J. Eden, P.A. Stott, D. J. Karoly, M.R. Allen. "The Attribution Question". <http://www.nature.com/nclimate/journal/v6/n9/full/nclimate3089.html#affil-auth> (2016): 813 – 816. doi:10.1038/nclimate3089. <https://www.nature.com/articles/nclimate3089#affil-auth>

6 References

Brugnara, Y. et al., 2019. The EUSTACE global land station daily air temperature dataset, submitted to *Geoscience Data Journal*

Durre, I., Menne, M. J., Gleason, B. E., Houston, T. G., & Vose, R. S. (2010). Comprehensive automated quality assurance of daily surface observations. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 49, 1615-1633.

Hunziker, S., Gubler, S., Calle Fernandez, J. M., Moreno, I., Andrade, M.F., Velarde, F., Carrasco, G., Castellón, Y., Croci-Maspoli, M., Konzelmann, T., Rohrer, M., & Brönnimann, S. (2017). Identifying, attributing, and overcoming common data quality issues of manned station observations. *International Journal of Climatology*, 37, 4131-4143.

Klein-Tank, A. M. G., Wijngaard, J. B., Können, G. P., Böhm, R., Demarée, G., Gocheva, A., et al. (2002). Daily dataset of 20th-century surface air temperature and precipitation series for the European Climate Assessment. *International Journal of Climatology*, 22, 1441-1453.

Menne, M. J., Durre, I., Vose, R. S., Gleason, B. E., & Houston, T. G. (2012). An overview of the global historical climatology network-daily database. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 29, 897-910.

Merchant, C., Ghent, D., Kennedy, J., Good, E., Hoeyer, J., 'Common approach to providing uncertainty estimates across all surfaces', EUSTACE Deliverable D1.2, 2015,
https://www.eustaceproject.org/eustace/static/media/uploads/Deliverables/eustace_d1-2.pdf

Rennie, J. J., Lawrimore, J. H., Gleason, B. E., Thorne, P. W., Morice, C. P., Menne, M. J., et al. (2014). The international surface temperature initiative global land surface databank: Monthly temperature data release description and methods. *Geoscience Data Journal*, 1, 75-102.

Stickler, A., Brönnimann, S., Valente, M. A., Bethke, J., Sterin, A., Jourdain, S., et al. (2014). ERA-CLIM: historical surface and upper-air data for future reanalyses. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 95, 1419-1430.012

A.A. Squintu, G. van der Schrier, Yuri Brugnara, Albert Klein Tank, 2018. Homogenization of daily temperature series in the European Climate Assessment & Dataset, *International Journal of Climatology*, doi.org/10.1002/joc.5874

van den Besselaar, E.J.M, A.M.G. Klein Tank, G. van der Schrier, P.D. Jones, 2012, Synoptic messages to extend climate data records, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 117, D07101, [doi:10.1029/2011JD016687](https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JD016687)

VIM (2012), *International Vocabulary of Metrology – Basic and General Concepts and Associated Terms (VIM 3rd edition) JCGM 200:2012 (JCGM 200:2008 with minor corrections)*

7 How to Cite the Datasets

Dataset	Recommended citation
EUSTACE / GlobTemperature: Global clear-sky land surface temperature from MODIS Aqua on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2002-2016	Ghent, D.; Veal, K.; Dodd, E. (2019): EUSTACE/GlobTemperature: Global clear-sky land surface temperature from MODIS Aqua on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2002-2016. Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, date of citation. http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/0f1a958a130547febd40057f5ec1c837
EUSTACE / GlobTemperature: Global clear-sky land surface temperature from MODIS Terra on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2002-2016	Ghent, D.; Veal, K.; Dodd, E. (2019): EUSTACE/GlobTemperature: Global clear-sky land surface temperature data from MODIS Terra on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v2.1, 2000-2016. Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, date of citation. http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/655866af94cd4fa6af67809657b275c3
EUSTACE / AASTI: Global clear-sky ice surface temperature from the AVHRR series on the satellite swath with estimates of uncertainty components, v1.0, 2000-2009	Coming soon
EUSTACE / CCI: Global clear-sky sea surface temperature from the (A)ATSR series at 0.25 degrees with estimates of uncertainty components, v1.2, 1991-2012	Coming soon
EUSTACE / ECA&D: European	Coming soon

land station daily air temperature measurements, homogenised	
EUSTACE: Global land station daily air temperature measurements with non-climatic discontinuities identified, for 1850-2015	Brugnara, Y.; Brönnimann, S.; Good, E.; Squintu, A.; van der Schrier, G. (2019): EUSTACE: Global land station daily air temperature measurements with non-climatic discontinuities identified, for 1850-2015. Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, date of citation. http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/7925ded722d743fa8259a93acc7073f2
EUSTACE: coincident daily air temperature estimates and reference measurements, for validation, 1850-2015	Coming soon
EUSTACE / E-OBS: Gridded European surface air temperature based on homogenised land station records since 1950	Coming soon
EUSTACE: Globally gridded clear-sky daily air temperature estimates from satellites with uncertainty estimates for land, ocean and ice, 1995-2016	Coming soon

EUSTACE: Global daily air temperature combining surface and satellite data, with uncertainty estimates, for 1850-2015	Coming soon
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Annex 1 **Glossary of terms and acronyms**

A

AASTI	Arctic and Antarctic Ice Surface Temperatures from thermal Infrared satellite sensors
AIRS	Atmospheric InfraRed Sounder
Air temperature	See section 2.1.1
ARM	Atmospheric Radiation Measurement programme
Average temperature	See section 2.1

C

CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CDG	Climate Data Guide (https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/)
CMSAF	EUMETSAT's Climate and Monitoring, Satellite Application Facility
CEDA	Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
CEMS	Climate and Environmental Monitoring from Space

D

DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
DOI	Digital Object Identifiers

E

EC	European Commission
ECA&D	European Climate Assessment Database (https://www.ecad.eu/)
ECV	Essential Climate Variables
E-OBS	gridded dataset based on data from ECA&D (https://www.ecad.eu/download/ensembles/ensembles.php)
ERA	ECMWF Reanalysis
ESA	European Space Agency
ESA CCI	European Space Agency Climate Change Initiative
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
EUSTACE	EU Surface Temperature for All Corners of Earth

F

FVC	Fraction of Vegetation Cover
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G

GHCN-D	Global Historical Climate Network – Daily
GlobTemp	GlobTemperature project (http://www.globtemperature.info/)

H

HadISD	Met Office Hadley Centre Integrated Surface Dataset
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I

IAT	Near surface air temperatures over ice
ICA&D	International Climate Assessment Database (https://www.ecad.eu/icad.php)
ICOADS	International Comprehensive Ocean-Atmosphere Data Set
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPCC DDC	IPCC Data Distribution Centre
IST	Ice Surface Temperature

J

JULES	Joint UK Land Environment Simulator
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K

KNMI Royal Dutch Meteorological Institute (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut)

L

Locally systematic uncertainty See section 2.1.

LSA-SAF EUMETSAT's Land Surface Analysis Satellite Application Facility

LSAT Land Surface Air Temperature

LST Land Surface Temperature

LSTday Daytime LST

LSTngt Night time LST

LSWT Lake Surface Water Temperature

M

MAD Mean Absolute Difference

MAT Marine Air Temperature

Mean temperature See section 2.1.1

MDB Matchup DataBase

MODIS MODerate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (satellite)

N

NACLIM North Atlantic CLIMate (project)

NASA National Aeronautics and Space Administration

NH Northern Hemisphere

NMAT Night time Marine Air Temperature

NWP Numerical Weather Prediction

O

OSI-SAF EUMETSAT's Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility

P

PROMICE PROGramme for Monitoring of the Greenland ICE Sheet

R

Random uncertainty See section 2.1.2.1

RMSD Root Mean Square Difference

S

SAF Satellite Application Facilities

SAT Surface Air Temperature

SEVIRI Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (satellite)

SH Southern Hemisphere

Skin temperature see section 2.1.

SST Sea Surface Temperature

STFC Science & Technology Facilities Council

Surface air temperature See section 2.1.1

Surface skin temperature See section 2.1.1

Systematic uncertainty See section 2

SZA Solar Zenith Angle

T

T2m Screen-level air temperature (at 2 m height, normally measured at in situ station)

Tavg Averaged daily T2m

Tmax Maximum daily T2m

Tmin Minimum daily T2m

Tskin Skin temperature (measured with satellite)

U

Uncertainty

See section 2.1.2

W

WP

Work package

Annex 2 Step-by-step example of how to access, visualise and process EUSTACE data with the Climate4impact portal

Coming soon

Annex 3 Links to some useful websites and tools

Below a selection of useful links is presented, based on suggestions from potential users and the knowledge of the partners within the EUSTACE project. On other sites also useful links, tools, etc. may be available. If you have more useful links that you want to share with others, send an e-mail to janette.besseminder@knmi.nl and we may include these in an update of this user guide or make them available through our website.

Portals to temperature datasets:

- Climate Data Guide: <https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data/global-temperature-datasets-overview-comparison-table>. With summaries, metadata, a comparison table and links to a large number of temperature datasets.
- ECA&D and ICA&D: European and International Climate Assessment Databases: <https://www.ecad.eu/>. Collects information on station observations in different parts of the world. Where the daily observations are not available, often derived indices and trends are freely available (for non-commercial use). Part of the functionalities is moved to Copernicus Climate Change Services websites.
- E-OBS: gridded dataset bases on data from ECA&D: <http://eca.knmi.nl/download/ensembles/ensembles.php>. Also a version with the homogenized temperature station data will be made available later on.
- Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S) Climate Data Store: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/#!/home>. Through this website a large number of climate data sets will be made available or is already available. The connected Toolbox offers a variety of processing and visualizing tools (or will provide this in the future).
- IPCC DCC: Data Distribution Centre: <http://www.ipcc-data.org/index.html>. With observational datasets and climate model simulations used for the various Assessment reports. Also guidance material available (<http://www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/index.html>)
- Climate Explorer: <https://climexp.knmi.nl/start.cgi>. Website where many observational, re-analysis and climate model data can be accessed and processed (especially for climate researchers)

Portals with tools to visualize, process, check datasets, etc.

- Climate data guide: <https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data-tools-and-analysis>. With a variety of tools for climate data processing.
- Climate data guide, Common Climate Data Formats: Overview: <https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data-tools-and-analysis/common-climate-data-formats-overview>. Also with some example codes to read, write or change data files
- Panoply: <https://www.giss.nasa.gov/tools/panoply/>. For viewing and processing of NetCDF, HDF and GRIB data sets (also mentioned in the Climate Data Guide).
- Climate4Impact portal: <https://climate4impact.eu/impactportal/general/index.jsp> and <https://climate4impact.eu/impactportal/data/esgfsearch.jsp>. Portal to access, visualize and process climate data. The ADAGUC viewer is used within this tool. A step-by-step guide with some examples on how to use the portal is included in Annex2 of this Product User Guide.
- KML tool: <https://developers.google.com/kml/documentation/>. Tool from Google to visualize and process data.

Background information:

- IPCC Glossary: https://www.ipcc.ch/pdf/assessment-report/ar5/syr/AR5_SYR_FINAL_Glossary.pdf. With many terms related to climate data, climate and climate change.
- General information about climate data. C3S User Learning Services: <https://uls.climate.copernicus.eu/login>. Portal for on-line learning about many aspects of climate data. Freely available, only registration needed. Related to the Climate Data Store of C3S. For those with very little knowledge about climate data the lesson/resource on “Introduction to climate data” may be a good introduction.
- Common Climate Data Formats: Overview. Climate Data Guide: <https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data-tools-and-analysis/common-climate-data-formats-overview>. Also with some example codes to read, write or change data files
- NetCDF: <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/> Potential users mentioned that there are some issues with NetCDF data used in certain packages . Check on internet whether this is the case when you encounter problems in a specific package.

Other related projects or initiatives:

- GlobTemperature: <http://www.globtemperature.info/>. Also with access to other LST (land Surface Temperature) products.

- ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI): <http://cci.esa.int>

Annex 4 Frequently Asked Questions